

EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT FIBER CROSS SECTION GEOMETRY ON INTERFACIAL DEBONDING BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Interfacial properties between matrix and reinforcement in composite materials are important because the material properties of composites depend on the interfacial properties. In this study, we conducted Single Fiber Pull-out tests of the model composites with round-shaped and gear-shaped reinforcements to evaluate the effect of the reinforcement cross section geometry on the interfacial properties. After the Pull-out test, we observed interface of the gear-shaped wire and found that debonding occurred along the outer surface of the wire and did not progress to the concave area of the gear. This unique interfacial debonding process of irregularly-shaped reinforcement may affect the increase of interfacial properties of composite materials by an effect like mechanical interlocking. Then we conducted stress analysis by Finite Element Method and found that stress distribution of the model with gear-shaped reinforcement is so unique. From both of experimental and numerical results, we expect that the gear-shaped reinforcement causes good interfacial properties by the mechanical interlocking effect. We discuss the cross-sectional geometry of the irregular-shaped reinforcement to induce the mechanical interlocking effect.

1 INTRODUCTION

For composite materials such as Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP), interfacial properties between their matrices and reinforcements are important because the material properties of composites depend on mechanical properties of the matrix and reinforcement and the interfacial properties. One of the ways for getting good interfacial properties is to use reinforcements which have irregularly-shaped cross section, instead of common round-shaped reinforcements. CFRP with irregularly-shaped carbon fiber like triangular-shaped[1], kidney-shaped[2] and C-shaped[3] have better material properties than CFRP with ordinary round-shaped carbon fiber, because of wider interfacial contact area between matrix and reinforcement[1–3].

However, besides effect of increasing contact area, we think that irregularly-shaped reinforcements might cause an additional effect like mechanical interlocking. For irregularly-shaped reinforcements, three-dimensional stress distribution at the interface is non-uniform, so that debonding of circumferential direction might be delayed.

To verify existence of this effect, we conducted single-fiber pull-out tests for evaluating interfacial properties on two types of model composites: one has ordinary round-shaped reinforcement, the other one has gear-shaped reinforcement as shown in Figure 1. Also, we made FEM model of the model composite with gear-shaped reinforcement and conducted stress analysis to discuss the debonding behavior in the gear-shaped reinforcement composites.

Figure 1: A schematic of round-shaped reinforcement (left) and gear-shaped reinforcement (right).

2 PULL-OUT TEST

2.1 Specimen

In this study, stainless steel wire and epoxy resin were used as reinforcement and matrix of model composite for pull-out test, respectively. As mentioned above, the cross sectional shapes of the wire are round and gear. For round-shaped wire (left one in Figure 1), three different diameters were used, which are 3, 4 and 5 mm. For gear-shaped wire (right one in Figure 1), outer diameter is 3.45 mm, inner diameter is 2.80 mm. The detailed cross-section geometry of the gear-shaped wire is shown in Figure 2.

The epoxy resin is cylindrical and its diameter is 45 mm. As specimen of pull-out test, one wire was embedded into the epoxy resin and its embedded length is 40 mm. A schematic of the specimen is shown in Figure 3, where $2a$ is wire diameter, $2b$ is matrix diameter, L is embedded length, F is pull-out load, $\tau_f(z)$ is interfacial shear stress, and r , θ and z are cylindrical coordinate axes.

Figure 2: The cross-section geometry of the gear-shaped wire.

Figure 3: A schematic of the specimen.

2.2 Interfacial properties

In constant displacement loading pull-out test, pull-out load F will drop when interfacial debonding occurs as shown in Figure 4, where $\delta_{ir,A}$ and $\delta_{ir,B}$ is residual displacement before debonding and after debonding respectively, Γ is energy consumed by debonding, U_{ir} is energy consumed by irreversible damage and U_{el} is energy consumed by elastic deformation[4]. This event will be occurred once or several times during a test. In this study, two interfacial properties, which are interfacial debonding energy release rate G_i and interfacial shear strength $\tau_{f,max}$ were evaluated for every events.

Interfacial debonding energy release rate G_i is energy consumption by debonding progress per unit area. That is,

$$G_i = \Gamma/S \quad (1)$$

The relation between interfacial debonding energy release rate G_i and applied stress on reinforcement at debonding σ_d is[5]

$$\sigma_d = 2 \sqrt{\frac{E_f E_c G_i}{a V_m E_m}} + \frac{2\tau E_c h}{a V_m E_m} \quad (2)$$

where E_f and E_c are Young's modulus of reinforcement and matrix, respectively, $V_m (= 1 - V_f)$ is volume fraction of the matrix, τ is average interfacial frictional stress, h is length of debonding progress and $E_c = V_f E_f + V_m E_m$. In Equation (2), first term on the right side is equivalent to the reinforcement axial stress at the bonded region σ_{bond} .

From reference [6], interfacial shear stress $\tau_f(z)$ of the pull-out test specimen is given by using shear-lag theory.

$$\tau_f(z) = \frac{b^2 - a^2}{2a} K \{D_1 \sinh(Kz) + D_2 \cosh(Kz)\} \quad (3)$$

where

$$D_1 = -\frac{a^2}{b^2 - a^2} \sigma_p \quad (4)$$

$$D_2 = \frac{a^2}{b^2 - a^2} \sigma_p \coth(KL) \quad (5)$$

$$K^2 = A_{12} \quad (6)$$

$$A_{12} = \frac{2}{a(b^2 - a^2)A_{11}} \frac{G_m E_f a^2 + E_m (b^2 - a^2)}{E_m} \quad (7)$$

$$A_{11} = \frac{ab^2}{2(b^2 - a^2)^2} \left\{ 2b^2 \ln \frac{b}{a} - (b^2 - a^2) \right\} - \frac{a}{4} \quad (8)$$

σ_p is applied stress on the reinforcement ($\sigma_p = F/\pi a^2$), and G_m is shear modulus of matrix. Obviously, equation (3) will be maximized at $z = 0$. Thus, interfacial shear strength τ_{fmax} is given by

$$\tau_{fmax} = \frac{a}{2} K \coth(KL) \sigma_{bond} \quad (9)$$

2.2 Observation of interfacial debonding progress

Length of debonding progress h is essential to evaluate interfacial properties. For measuring the debonding length h , photoelastic method was used in this study. When stress concentration occurs at debonded tip, photoelastic interference fringes also concentrate at the same point. Therefore, we can see debonded tip and measure the length of debonding progress h . A specimen is placed between two polarization plates to get photoelastic image and we recorded it by CCD camera. Figure 5 shows an example image which we recorded.

Figure 4: Schematic of load-displacement diagram and energy balance at interfacial debonding[4].

Figure 5: A photoelastic image of the interfacial debonding.

Figure 6: Load-displacement diagram of specimen with round-shaped wire.

Figure 7: Load-displacement diagram of specimen with gear-shaped wire.

Figure 8: Interfacial debonding energy release rate vs. wire diameter plot.

Figure 9: Interfacial shear strength vs. wire diameter plot.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Load-displacement diagram

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show load-displacement diagram of specimens with round-shaped wire (the diameter of 3 mm) and gear-shaped wire, respectively. Because residual displacement just before debonding development was needed for evaluating interfacial debonding energy, we estimated it using the slopes of the unloading-reloading cycles conducted during the pull-out test as shown in Figures Figure 6 and Figure 7.

On the specimens with gear-shaped wire, load drop without detection of any debonding progress occurred more times than round-shaped ones. We consider that this is because debonding progressed in blind area, such as behind of the wire or inside of the teeth of the gear, so we couldn't observe debonding progress by the photoelastic method.

3.2 Interfacial properties

We conducted pull-out test on the specimen with round-shaped wire and gear-shaped wire, and then evaluated interfacial debonding energy release rate G_i and interfacial shear strength τ_{fmax} . Figure 8 shows interfacial debonding energy release rate versus wire diameter plot and Figure 9 shows interfacial shear strength versus wire diameter plot. Blue circle symbols indicate specimens with round-shaped wire and red square symbols indicate ones with gear-shaped wire.

From both interfacial property plots, we can't find any tendencies. These values are scattering, this is because we couldn't measure the length of debonding progress h exactly. Measuring method used in this study is limited to two-dimensional observation so that can't observe three-dimensional debonding progress.

3.3 Microscopic observation on the interface

After the Pull-out test, we observed interface of the gear-shaped wire by optical microscope. A microscopic image of the interface between gear-shaped wire and epoxy resin is shown in Figure 10. From this picture, we consider that debonding had occurred along the outer surface of the wire and proceeded to the next edge of the tooth without penetrating into the concave area of the gear.

Figure 10: Interface between gear-shaped wire and epoxy resin after the pull-out test.

4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSES

From experimental results debonding process on the specimen with gear-shaped wire was so unique and may affect the increase of interfacial properties of composite materials by an effect like mechanical interlocking. To verify this unique debonding process, we conducted stress analysis by Abaqus 6.14.

4.1 Pull-out model with gear-shaped wire

As shown in Figure 2, the gear-shaped wire has eight teeth so we made one eighth model (called Gear-original model) which is cyclic symmetry. The FEM mesh of this model is shown in Figure 11. We applied unit displacement loading to the top end of the wire and constrained displacement in the normal direction on the top surface of the epoxy as like the pull-out test.

Figure 12 shows von Mises stress distribution in the epoxy of the Gear-original model. This stress distribution is normalized by the applied stress on top of the wire. In Figure 12, we can see that stress is higher at the corner of the outer surface of the gear-shaped wire than in the concave area of the wire. We consider that the higher stress distribution had caused the crack to grow in the outer region and not to extend to the concave region. This unique stress distribution might cause enhancement of interfacial properties by an effect like mechanical interlocking.

4.2 Discussing the cross-section geometry of the gear-shaped wire

To induce this effect like mechanical interlocking, we changed parameters of the cross-section of the gear-shape wire, and made FEM models to conduct stress analyses. Gear-original model is a standard and the same as the wire geometry in experiment. Gear-PH model has the same perimeter to Gear-original but higher teeth than Gear-original. Gear-PL model is also the same in its perimeter but has lower teeth than Gear-original. Gear-AH model has the same cross-sectional area to Gear-original but higher teeth than Gear-original. Figures Figure 13, Figure 14, Figure 15 and Figure 16 show normalized von Mises stress distribution in Gear-original, Gear-PH, Gear-PL and Gear-AH, respectively.

Figure 17 shows normalized von Mises stress variations along the wire-epoxy interface in each model. From this figure, we can see that stress along the interface in Gear-PH and Gear-AH are smaller than Gear-original and Gear-PL. This means that gear-shaped reinforcement which has high teeth leads to decrease stress along the interface and may delay interfacial debonding in comparison with round-shaped reinforcement.

Figure 11: An overview of the FEM mesh of the Gear-original model.

Figure 12: Von Mises stress distribution of the Gear-original model.

Figure 13: Stress distribution in Gear-original model.

Figure 14: Stress distribution in Gear-PH model.

Figure 15: Stress distribution in Gear-PL model.

Figure 16: Stress distribution in Gear-AH model.

Figure 17: Stress variation along the wire-epoxy interface.

5 CONCLUSION

We conducted pull-out test on the specimens with round-shaped wire and gear-shaped wire to evaluate interfacial properties. However, their interfacial properties didn't indicate any tendencies because interfacial debonding behavior in the specimens was not detected precisely. From microscopic observation after the tests, we found that debonding occurred along the outer surface of the gear-shaped wire. Besides, we conducted stress analysis on the model composite with gear-shaped reinforcement by FEM and the stress distribution was so unique that might cause good interfacial properties by an effect like mechanical interlocking. FEM results showed stress on the interface of gear-shaped reinforcement and matrix would be smaller in the higher teeth gear composites than in the lower teeth ones. This means interfacial debonding in composite which contains irregular-shaped reinforcement with high teeth would be delayed in comparison with ordinal round-shaped reinforcement composites. This might be more effective when the irregular-shaped reinforcement is more convex.

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